

Synthesis, Characterization and Evaluation of Bioactive Potential of Gold Nanoparticles Fabricated Using *Ocimum Sanctum* Inflorescence

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Abstract

Nanotechnology involves the synthesis, characterization, and application of nanoparticles, which range in size from 1 to 99 nm and possess unique properties compared to their bulk counterparts. In this study, a green synthesis approach was employed to fabricate gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) using the extract of dried panicles of *Ocimum sanctum* (holy basil). The synthesis was confirmed by a color change from yellow to magenta, and UV-Vis spectroscopy revealed a characteristic peak at 550 nm, indicating successful nanoparticle formation. Characterization techniques highlighted their distinct properties: FTIR spectroscopy identified functional groups responsible for nanoparticle synthesis, dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis showed a particle size of 87.6 nm and a zeta potential of -17.0 mV, suggesting good stability, and SEM analysis revealed a non-uniform surface structure with an average size of 75.6 nm and a spherical shape. The synthesized AuNPs were evaluated for bioactive potential. Although they showed no DPPH free radical scavenging activity, they demonstrated notable antimicrobial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, with a 20 mm zone of inhibition. Furthermore, the nanoparticles exhibited remarkable dye degradation potential, achieving efficiencies of 80.07%, 80.43%, 82.59%, 88.15%, and 91.92% at concentrations of 100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 μ L, respectively. This study highlights the potential of *Ocimum sanctum*-derived gold nanoparticles as a sustainable solution for antibacterial and dye degradation applications, showcasing their promise in environmental and biomedical fields.

Key words: Nanotechnology, green synthesis, gold nanoparticles, *Ocimum Sanctum*, bioactive compounds, antimicrobial activity, Dye degradation, Dynamic light scattering, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy, UV-Vis spectroscopy, sustainable nanomaterials.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology, the science of manipulating matter at the nanoscale, has revolutionized multiple disciplines by enabling the synthesis of nanoparticles with unique and enhanced properties [1]. Nanoparticles, typically ranging from 1 to 99 nm in size, exhibit distinct physicochemical characteristics compared to their bulk counterparts, making them highly versatile for applications in medicine, environmental remediation, and material science [2]. Among these, gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have gained particular attention due to their stability, biocompatibility, and potential bioactivities. Green synthesis of nanoparticles has emerged as a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to conventional chemical methods, utilizing natural extracts as reducing and stabilizing agents [3]. *Ocimum sanctum* (holy basil), a medicinal plant rich in bioactive phytochemicals, provides an excellent source for such green synthesis [4]. This study explores the synthesis of gold nanoparticles using *Ocimum sanctum* panicle extract and evaluates their bioactive properties, focusing on antibacterial, antioxidant and dye degradation potentials. This eco-friendly approach highlights the dual benefits of sustainability and the utilization of plant-derived nanomaterials for diverse applications.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

Ocimum sanctum plant panicles, Blender, weighing balance, magnetic stirrer, conical flask, beakers, test tubes, petri plates, Whatman NO.1 filter paper.

Reagents: - Hydro tetra chloro aurate, Textile dye (violet)

B. Methods

a) *Collection of sample:*

Panicles of *Ocimum sanctum* were collected from the Vidyanagar region in Tirupati.

Fig 1. Dried panicles of *Ocimum Sanctum*

b) *Processing of sample:*

The collected panicles were dried and ground into a fine powder using a blender. 2.5 grams of the powder was accurately weighed using a weighing balance. The finely ground powder was then dispersed in 50 mL of distilled water.

c) *Extraction and synthesis:*

The mixture was heated and stirred on a magnetic stirrer hot plate for 30 minutes. The extract of *Ocimum sanctum* panicles was collected in a conical flask and filtered using Whatman No.1 filter paper. Subsequently, 2 mL of the filtrate was transferred into a conical flask, and an equal volume (2 mL) of Hydro tetra chloro aurate (HAuCl₄) solution was added in a 1:1 ratio.

Fig 2. Preparation of extract and synthesis of nanoparticles

d) *Characterization of gold nanoparticles:*

The nano particles were characterized by following techniques.

- UV - Visible spectrophotometry
- DLS (Particles size – zetapotential analysis)
- FTIR (Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy)
- SEM (Scanning electron microscopy)

UV-Visible spectrophotometry:

The optical properties of the nanoparticles were analyzed using a Nanodrop-8000, while a UV-Visible spectrometer was employed to record the absorption spectrum and identify the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) band.

FTIR Spectroscopy:

The FTIR spectrum was recorded using an Alpha BRUKER Transmission spectrometer to analyze the presence of functional groups in the extract and the synthesis mixture.

DLS analysis:

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) is a widely accepted technique for measuring particle size in a hydrosol. In this study, the particle size and zeta potential of the nanoparticles were determined using the SZ-100 Nanoparticle Analyzer (Horiba).

SEM (Scanning electron microscopy):

The nanoparticles were mounted on the copper stubs and the images were studied using scanning electron microscope (Jeol 639LA\OXFORD XMXN) with secondary electron detector at an opening voltage of 20KV.

e) *Bioactivity validation of nanoparticles:*

Antimicrobial activity:

The antimicrobial activity of the extract was assessed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method (Biemer, 1973). Nutrient broth was used to culture the test organisms, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus subtilis*. Actively growing cultures (20 µL) of the test organisms were evenly spread onto nutrient agar plates. Sterile discs impregnated with varying concentrations of the extract or nanoparticles (100 µg, 200 µg, 300 µg, 400 µg, and 500 µg) were placed equidistantly on the agar plates. The plates were then incubated for 24 hours to observe and measure the zones of inhibition.

Antioxidant activity:

The free radical scavenging activity of the extract was evaluated using the DPPH radical scavenging assay. [] A methanolic solution of DPPH (0.004% w/v) was added to the extracts at varying concentrations (100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 µg/mL) prepared in 1 mL of DMSO. After a 30-minute incubation period at room temperature in the dark, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm against a blank. Ascorbic acid was used as the standard reference. Each test was performed in triplicate, and the results were averaged. The percentage inhibition (I%) of DPPH-derived free radicals was calculated using the following equation.

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{A(\text{control}) - A(\text{sample})}{A(\text{control})} \times 100$$

Dye degradation potential:

1 ml of 1000 ppm violet dye was prepared in distilled water and added to 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 µl Conc. Of nanoparticle colloid and incubated at room temperature for 24 hours.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

A. Extraction and synthesis result:

The *Ocimum sanctum* plant inflorescence extract induced synthesized gold nanoparticles were primarily confirmed by a change of colour from yellow to magenta colour.

B. UV – Visible spectroscopy:

In this study, UV spectroscopic analysis was conducted for both the OSP extract and the gold nanoparticles synthesized using the extract. The extract and nanoparticles exhibited distinct peaks, with a characteristic peak at 550 nm wavelength specific to the synthesized gold nanoparticles. This peak confirms the successful synthesis of the gold nanoparticles.

Fig 3. UV spectrum of extract (black) and OSP (red)

C. DLS Analysis:

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis confirmed the particle size of the synthesized gold nanoparticles to be 87.6 nm, placing them within the nanoscale range of 1–99 nm. The zeta potential of the nanoparticles was measured at -17.0 mV, indicating good stability. These results demonstrate that the synthesized nanoparticles are both within the nano size range and exhibit sufficient stability.

Fig 4. DLS analysis particle size

Table I

Peak No.	S.P Area Ratio	Mean	S.D.	Mode
1	1.00	93.4nm	23.2 nm	87.6 nm
2	---	---nm	---nm	---nm
3	---	---nm	---nm	---nm
Total	1.00	93.4nm	23.2 nm	87.6 nm

Z-Average : 1112.8 nm

PI : 0.369 nm

Fig 5. DLS zeta potential analysis

TABLE II

Peak no	Zeta potential	Electrophoretic mobility
1	-17.0 Mv	-0.000132 cm ² /Vs
2	--- Mv	--- cm ² / Vs
3	--- mV	--- cm ² / Vs

Zeta potential (Mean) : -17.0 Mv

Electrophoretic Mobility Mean : -0.000132 cm² / Vs

D. Scanning electrom microscopy (SEM) analysis:

The surface morphology of gold nanoparticles synthesized from the plant extract was analyzed using SEM imaging, as shown in the figure. The SEM images revealed that the nanoparticles were predominantly spherical in shape, with non-uniform grain sizes. The grains appeared loosely packed

and porous, with sizes ranging from 75.6 nm to 147 nm, indicating a non-uniform distribution. Additionally, some nanoparticles exhibited oval and elliptical shapes. Such variations in shape and size are commonly observed in nanoparticles synthesized through biological methods.

Fig 6. SEM images showing the size, morphology and texture of gold nanoparticles as obtained from the *Ocimum sanctum* panicles.

E. FTIR spectroscopic analysis:

Medium peaks observed at 3318.99 cm^{-1} and 3321.12 cm^{-1} suggest the potential involvement of aliphatic amines, while the peak at 1637 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of cyclic alkenes. These functional groups likely play a role in the synthesis and stabilization of the gold nanoparticles.

SAMPLE SCANS : 24
DATE : 23-04-2024
TIME : 11:22:28

SAMPLE : OSP Extra
TECHNIQUE : LIQUID
USER : LabManager

Fig 7. OSP Extract Sample

Fig 8. OSP AuNPs sample

F. Bioactivity validations:

I. Antibacterial activity:

The results of the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion assay revealed that gold nanoparticles synthesized using *Ocimum sanctum* panicle extract exhibited an inhibitory effect against the human pathogenic bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*, with a zone of inhibition measuring 20 mm. However, the nanoparticles showed no inhibitory activity against other tested pathogens. The diameter of the zones of inhibition was measured after 24 hours of incubation, providing insights into the antimicrobial potential of the synthesized

nanoparticles.

- a) Escherichia coli
- b) Pseudomonas aeruginosa
- c) Staphylococcus aureus
- d) Bacillus subtilis

Fig 9. Antibacterial activity of *Ocimum Sanctum* gold nanoparticles against bacterial pathogens namely a) *Escherichia coli* b) *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* c) *Staphylococcus aureus* d) *Bacillus subtilis*

TABLE III

ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF THE SAMPLE AGAINST BACTERIAL PATHOGENS

OSP AuNps Conc.(mcg/ml)	Zones of inhibition in mm on test pathogen			
	<i>Escherichia Coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
100	0	0	0	0
200	0	0	0	0
300	0	0	0	0
400	0	0	20	0
Standard	25	30	25	15

II. Anti-oxidant activity analysis:

OSP-AuNPs were found to exhibit no significant antioxidant activity. In contrast, ascorbic acid, used as the standard, demonstrated a strong free radical scavenging effect.

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{A(\text{control}) - A(\text{sample})}{A(\text{control})} \times 100$$

A – Absorbance

TABLE IV

Sample	100	200	300	400	500
OSP AuNps	0	0	0	0	0
Ascorbic acid (Conc. $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	34.18 (25)	47.24 (50)	58.4 (75)	78.36 (100)	100 (150)

Fig. 10 Vials containing OSP-AuNP solutions at varying concentrations were prepared for the evaluation of antioxidant activity.

III. Dye degradation analysis:

The catalytic dye degradation potential of OSP-AuNPs was assessed using a textile violet dye solution. The absorbance of the treated samples was measured, and the percentage of dye degradation was calculated using the following formula:

$$Ci - Ct / Ci \times 100$$

Where, C_i is the initial conc. Of dye, C_t is the conc. of dye after time(t)

The nanoparticles exhibited remarkable dye – degradation potential with 80.07, 80.43, 82.59, 88.15, and 91.92 % at 100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 μL Conc. respectively

Fig 11. Dye degradation potential of OSP AuNPs at different conc.

TABLE V

Conc. Of AuNPs	Degradation
100	80.07
200	80.43
300	82.59
400	88.15
500	91.92

IV. CONCLUSION

Green production of nanoparticles is gaining prominence due to its advantages over physical and chemical approaches. In the current study, gold nanoparticles were synthesised using *Ocimum sanctum* panicles extract. The synthesised nanoparticles were characterised and appraised for their potential applications. They were found to have an antibacterial action. The nanoparticles showed dye degradation potential. Further research could lead to exploring their other biological activities and structural elucidation.

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